

Full Length Research Paper

Antibiogram of some bacteria isolated from processed tiger-nut beverage (Kunun-Aya) sold in the University of Jos community Plateau State Nigeria

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An investigation was conducted to determine the antibiogram of some bacterial species isolated from locally processed Tiger-nut drink "Kunun-Aya" sold in University of Jos. The isolation, identifications, bacteria counts and antibiotic resistance pattern of the isolates against some antibiotics were done using standard microbiological techniques. The bacteriological analyses revealed the presence of three genera of bacteria species; *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Salmonella* spp with varying degrees of occurrences. The highest coliform counts ranged from (4.8×10^7 cfu/ml) to (3.1×10^7 cfu/ml). Antibiogram of the bacterial isolates revealed a varying level of resistance and susceptibility to the antibiotics tested. All the bacterial isolates were susceptible to Trimethoprim-Sulfamethoxazole. Conversely, all the isolates were highly resistant to Chloramphenicol, Sparfloxacin, Amoxicillin,

Perfloxacin, Erythromycin, Amoxicillin/Clavulanate and Streptomycin except *Salmonella* spp. which was highly susceptible to Ciprofloxacin. Based on the result of this finding, it can be concluded that the bacterial isolates had varying levels of resistance to the antibiotics tested. The antibiotic resistance pattern exhibited by the isolates from the Tiger-nut drink 'Kunun-Aya' is indicative of possible abuse of the use of antibiotics and that the consumption of this beverage has potential public health implications and subsequent chemotherapeutic failures in the consumers of this local beverage in the University of Jos community.

Keywords: Antibiogram, pathogenic bacteria, Tiger-Nut beverage (Kunun-Aya), University of Jos

INTRODUCTION

Cultivation of tiger nuts started since early times (chiefly in South Europe and West Africa) for its small tuberous rhizomes, which can be eaten raw, roasted, dried, baked or made into a refreshing beverage (tiger-nut milk) called 'Kunun-Aya' in Hausa. Its plant grows easily and is consumed widely in Nigeria and in other parts of West Africa. Tiger-nut (*Cyperus esculentus*) can be found wild, as a weed, or as a crop (Abaejoh *et al.*, 2007). Kunun-Aya drink is a locally prepared indigenous non-alcoholic beverage that is widely produced and consumed in Nigeria (Umar *et al.*, 2014).

'Kunun-Aya' is a locally produced juice that is widely consumed as drink in many African countries including Nigeria, and has been reported to contain high nutritional

values (Ayo and Okaka, 1998). The juice is white in colour and refreshing especially when chilled. It is a traditional non-alcoholic beverage with a spicy nutty taste. It is widely consumed for its nutritional and medicinal benefits to its consumers and for its non-alcoholic properties. It has immense social, economic, nutritional and medicinal benefits (Abegaz, 2006). Tiger-nut milk drink like other locally made drinks is widely consumed in Nigeria (Abegaz, 2006).

Kunun-Zaki drink is a locally prepared indigenous non-alcoholic beverage which is widely produced and consumed in Nigeria, especially the northern part of the country (Amusa and Ashaye, 2009). This local beverage is consumed in both wet and dry seasons because of its

optimal thirst quenching abilities. The ingredients used are usually not quantified and are very unique because they are sourced locally (Maji *et al.*, 2011).

In spite of the important role of 'Kunun-Aya', a popular drink among the northerners served at events to give guests a refreshing taste because of its optimal thirst quenching abilities, its nutritional values and medicinal benefits; the production of the product is mostly done in rural areas by people with poor hygiene practice (Belewu and Abodunrin, 2008). The water content coupled with the 'crude' method of production and packaging that is made under unsatisfactory sanitary conditions predisposes the drink to microbial contamination (Akoma *et al.*, 2012). The ubiquitous nature of bacteria guarantees them the opportunity to be found in this locally made beverage and possibly from the water used for its preparation during storage and other processes involved in its preparation (Belewu and Abodunrin, 2008). 'Kunun-Aya' is a well-known good medium that supports the growth of several microorganisms with resultant spoilage of the product or infections and intoxications in consumers (Defelice, 2002).

The whole world is filled with a bewildering array of infectious agents (Baby-Joseph *et al.*, 2011). In Nigeria, the traditional method of processing and selling tiger-nut juice exposes the product to the danger of microbial contamination from spoilage and pathogenic microorganisms (Umar *et al.*, 2014). The drink can also be re-contaminated directly by handlers, utensils used in the preparation and other external sources (Makut *et al.*, 2014). Though researches have been carried out in other places in relation to this local beverage, this study is the first of its kind in University of Jos community on the antibiotic resistance patterns of bacteria isolated from this beverage. Thus, this study's objective is to determine the antibiogram of some pathogenic bacteria associated with Kunun-Aya drink in the University of Jos community.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study area

This work was carried out in Jos metropolis, Jos North Local Government of Plateau State, Nigeria and the microbiological analyses were conducted in the Microbiology Laboratory of the Department of Microbiology, University of Jos. University of Jos community is geographically situated on a latitude of 9° 57' 1" and longitude of 8° 53' 21" E.

Sample collection

300 ml of 'Kunun-Aya' in triplicates were aseptically obtained from local sellers in test tubes at random from five different locations (Administrative block, Department

of Physics, Remedial Sciences Physics laboratory, Beside Department of Architecture and NNPC shop Abuja Hostel) in the University of Jos community and conveyed to the microbiology laboratory of the University of Jos for analysis. The samples were collected in sterile sampling bottles and were immediately transported in an ice-packed box within temperature range of 4-6°C to the laboratory for analyses (Obiekezie *et al.*, 2012). 10 ml out of 300 ml sample was aseptically transferred by means of sterile pipette into 90 ml of sterile diluents (0.1% peptone water). Serial dilutions were prepared up to 10⁻⁴ for total bacterial count. Standard bacteriological methods were employed for the isolation of bacteria as recommended by Cheesbrough, (2006).

Determination of aerobic plate count

Standard plate count method was used to determine the total aerobic colony counts of bacteria in the samples of the five different locations. A ten-fold serial dilution of the samples from each of the different locations were performed and plated out on nutrient agar with dilution factor of 10⁻⁴ using pour plate technique. The average bacterial loads of the different locations were expressed as colony forming units per ml (cfu/mL).

Isolation and identification of bacterial isolates from 'kunun-Aya'

Nutrient agar was used as a general medium for total viable count. MacConkey agar was used for enumerating total coliform counts and to isolate lactose fermenting gram negative bacteria, Eosin methylene blue, mannitol salt agar and Salmonella-Shigella agar were used for the total faecal coliform count and selective isolation of enteric coliforms respectively. MacConkey agar was used to isolate lactose fermenting gram negative bacteria; Eosin methylene blue was used for the selective isolation of enteric Coliforms, mannitol salt agar was used for the selective isolation of salt-tolerant gram positive bacteria (*Staphylococcus aureus*) while Salmonella-Shigella agar was used for the isolation of *Salmonella* species. All plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 h for microbial growth. All plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 h (Odu *et al.*, 2011; Makut *et al.*, 2014). Identification of the isolates was based on cultural, morphological and biochemical characteristics as recommended by Holt, (1994).

Antimicrobial susceptibility test

The bacterial isolates were screened for antimicrobial susceptibility using the Kirby-Bauer agar disk diffusion method as described by CLSI, (2009). A suspension of each isolate was prepared in peptone water to match 0.5

McFarland turbidity standards in order to standardize the inoculum. The standardized inoculum of each isolate was then inoculated in triplicates onto the surfaces of plain Mueller-Hinton agar plates and Trimethoprim-Sulfamethoxazole (30 µg), Chloramphenicol (30 µg), Sparfloxacin (10 µg), Amoxicillin (30 µg), Ciprofloxacin (10 µg) Amoxicillin/Clavulanate (30 µg), Gentamicin (10 µg), Pefloxacin (30 µg), Ofloxacin (10 µg) and Streptomycin (30 µg) discs were placed aseptically on the inoculated plates and incubated at 37°C for 24 h. The zones of inhibition was measured and compared with the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) guidelines (CLSI, 2009).

Statistical analysis

The data obtained were analyzed using the Statistical package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software version 16. Chi square test was used to compare the frequency of occurrence of the bacterial isolates in relation to locations. The *p*-value > 0.05 was considered statistically not significant.

Results

The total aerobic bacterial mean counts of ‘Kunun-Aya’ sold at different locations in University of Jos community

Table 1 shows the total aerobic bacterial mean counts of ‘Kunun-Aya’ sold at the different locations in University of Jos community. The counts ranged from 3.1 × 10⁷ to 4.8 × 10⁷ cfu/mL in the Administrative block and Department of Architecture where the lowest and the highest bacterial mean counts were recorded respectively.

Table 1. Total bacterial mean counts (cfu/mL) of processed ‘Kunun-Aya’ sold in five different locations within University of Jos community.

Locations	‘Kunun-Aya’ drink
A	3.8 × 10 ⁷
B	3.4 × 10 ⁷
C	3.1 × 10 ⁷
D	3.3 × 10 ⁷
E	4.8 × 10 ⁷

Key: A = Physics department; B = Remedial Sciences Physics laboratory; C = Administrative block; D = NNPC shop Abuja hostel; E = Beside Department of Architecture; MCA= MacConkey Agar medium
 EMB= Eosin Methylene Blue Agar medium
 MSA= Manitol Salt Agar medium
 SSA= Salmonella-Shigella Agar medium

The percentage occurrence of different bacterial species

Cultural, morphological and biochemical tests confirm the presence of the following bacteria: *E. coli*, *Salmonella* spp. and *S. aureus*. *E. coli* was the most predominant isolate with 100% occurrence followed by *Salmonella* spp. and *S. aureus* having percentage occurrence of 20% each (Table 2).

Antibiogram of the bacterial isolates from ‘Kunun Aya’

Table 3 shows the Antibiotic resistance patterns of the bacterial species isolated from ‘Kunun-Aya’ drinks sold in the University of Jos community. The results show that *Salmonella* spp. exhibited 100% resistance to Trimethoprim-Sulfamethoxazole 57% resistance to chloramphenicol, and 33% resistance to amoxicillin, whereas there was no resistance to Ciprofloxacin (10 µg) at 0%. The percentage resistance of *S. aureus* was relatively low which ranged from 26% to 13% in Ciprofloxacin and Gentamicin respectively. The highest percentage resistance was recorded for Chloramphenicol with about 26%, Ciprofloxacin gave 26%, and Amoxicillin with 26% respectively, and the least resistance was recorded for Gentamicin with about 13% and Ofloxacin with 13%. Similarly, the percentage resistance of *E. coli* was recorded for Pefloxacin with 100% as the highest, and the least resistance was recorded for Ofloxacin with 9%.

DISCUSSION

The bacterial loads of the samples collected from the five different locations were relatively high. Presumptive isolation and identification of bacterial isolates indicate the presence of *Staphylococcus aureus*, *E. coli* and *Salmonella* spp. This indicates microbial contamination of this local drink. Most of the bacterial organisms isolated in this study were earlier reported by Musa and Hamza, (2013), Umar *et al.* (2014), Makut *et al.* (2013, 2014), Susan *et al.* (2014) and Falegan and Akele, (2014) in locally processed fermented milk (Nono). The bacterial load obtained from this study ranged from 3.1×10⁷-4.8× 10⁷ cfu/ml is indicative of the fact that ‘Kunun-Aya’ drink sold in all the locations (A, B, C and D) had insignificant mean values of bacteria loads except location E which is varied. This corroborates the findings of Belewu and Abodunrin, (2008), Abegaz (2007), and Nwosu *et al.* (2014) Akoma *et al.* (2012). This also suggests that similar handling procedures were employed during processing and marketing of the product. Therefore, they may have similar or different microbial quality. Lack of effective precautionary measures on hygiene practice in handling procedures during processing of the drink may

Table 2. Bacterial isolates from sample of 'Kunun-Aya' sold in different locations.

Bacterial isolates	Locations					Percentage occurrence (%)
	A	B	C	D	E	
<i>E. coli</i>	+	+	+	+	+	100
<i>Salmonella</i> sp.	-	-	-	-	+	20
<i>S. aureus</i>	+	-	-	-	-	20

Key: + = Positive; - = Negative; A = Physics department; B = Remedial Sciences Physics laboratory; C = Administrative block; D = NNPC shop Abuja Hostel; E =Beside Department of Architecture.

Table 3. Antibiogram of the bacterial isolates from 'Kunun Aya'.

Antibiotics	Conc. (µg)	<i>Salmonella</i> sp. (%)	<i>S. aureus</i> (%)	<i>E. coli</i> (%)	
Trimethoprim-Sulfamethoxazole	30		100	22	57
Chloramphenicol	30		57	26	37
Sparfloxacin	10		24	22	24
Ciprofloxacin	10		00	26	13
Amoxicillin	30		33	26	11
Clavulanate	30		22	17	22
Gentamicin	10		17	13	24
Pefloxacin	30		22	17	100
Ofloxacin	10		04	13	09
Streptomycin	30		30	17	20

be attributed to the high microbial counts in the drink. This result is in conformity with the report of Umar *et al.* (2014) who studied the bacteriological quality of 'Kunun-Aya' (tiger nut juice) sold at Umaru Musa Yar'adua University campus, Katsina. This is similar to the work done by Makut *et al.*, (2014) who reported that the handling practices of the 'Fulani' women might have contributed to the high bacteria counts of the locally processed cow milk products sold in Keffi Metropolis. The quantity and quality of water that is usually added during processing could also have served as a source of introducing microbial contaminants present in the water or from the utensils used. This is in agreement with Amusa and Ashaye, (2009) and Nwosu *et al.* (2014), who reported that the presence of coliforms such as *E. coli* in hawked 'Kunun zaki' was a result of contaminated water, containers, as well as dirty environment where the 'Kunun zaki' were processed and hawked. The antibiotic resistant pattern of the bacterial isolates is in agreement with reports of earlier researchers (Udo *et al.*, 2001; Soomro *et al.*, 2002; Inyang, 2009; Tagoe *et al.*, 2011; Makut *et al.*, 2013, 2014). For most bacteria, there is evidence that increased usage of a particular antimicrobial correlates with increased levels of bacterial resistance (Granizo *et al.*, 2000); perhaps this explains the high resistance to Amoxicillin by the isolates because of its common and prevalent use.

Three genera of bacteria were isolated from the 'Kunun Aya' samples and these were *E. coli*, *Salmonella* sp. and *S. aureus*. The presence of these organisms is a matter of serious concern. The bacterial species isolated were

pathogenic. The organisms detected have serious public health implication. *S. aureus* causes diseases in humans as it is responsible for a long list of different diseases such as folliculitis, furuncles, carbuncles, erysipelas, cellulitis, scalded skin syndrome, impetigo, pneumonia, osteoporosis, toxic shock syndrome (toxemia), meningitis, and staphylococcal food poisoning (Marjorie and Kathleen, 2006; Abdulkadir and Mugadi, 2012).

Steward and Besorick (1997) opined that *Salmonella* spp. is a strict pathogen and has no habitat other than humans and animals body, and that source of human infection is therefore from human and animal carriers; where the organism is excreted in the faeces or urine and transmitted by food or water which is ingested by another subject. *Salmonella* spp. can cause bacterial food poisoning, enteric fever and systemic fever (Steward and Besorick, 1997).

The presence of coliform bacteria in 'Kunun-Aya' drinks as established in this study is of health concern because students relies on these drinks as cheaper alternative to the bottled soft drinks. The incidence of *E. coli* in the "Kunun Aya" from this study could be harmful to consumers because it is related to food borne diseases. The risk is magnified when the local beverage is contaminated with *Salmonella* spp which can survive at temperatures of refrigeration where these "Kunun-Aya" drinks are normally stored. This also agreed with the work of Hahn, (1996).

The Antibiogram of the isolates revealed varying levels of resistance and susceptibility to the antibiotics tested. All the bacterial isolates were susceptible to Trimethoprim

-Sulfamethoxazole. Conversely, all the isolates were highly resistant to Chloramphenicol, Sparfloxacin, Amoxicillin, Perfloracin, Erythromycin, Amoxicillin/Clavulanate and Streptomycin except *Salmonella* sp which was highly susceptible to Ciprofloxacin. The sensitivity of these isolates to some of the antibiotics tested is in agreement with the report by Makut *et al.* (2013) who demonstrated that Kunun-zaki sold in Keffi is contaminated with potentially pathogenic bacteria including antibiotic resistant *E. coli* which may lead to failures in antibiotic chemotherapy among consumers.

This study was also in agreement to a report by Nwosu *et al.* (2014, 2017) who stated that *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, *Klebsiella* spp, *P. aeruginosa*, *P. vulgaris* and *Salmonella* spp isolates are highly susceptible to Gentamicin and Chloramphenicol due to their requirement for parenteral administration which discourage abuse and misuse. The public health implication of the findings of this study is that, antimicrobial resistant strains of pathogenic bacteria may colonize the human population through consumption of contaminated 'Kunun Aya' and this would lead to chemotherapeutic failures in human consumers of this popular beverage in the University of Jos community.

Conclusion

The results obtained in this study shows that there are presence of pathogenic bacteria that may be potential source of food borne infection and some related diseases for the consumers of this product in the studied areas. The total viable bacteria counts in the samples analyzed were above the recommended standard.

According to Nigerian Agency for Food, Drugs Administration and Control NAFDAC (2000), the microbial load limited for total liable colony count is 1.0×10^2 cfu/ml and that *Escherichia coli* should not be present in all food samples. However, *E. coli* was confirmed to be present in almost all the samples analyzed in this study.

This study also demonstrates the occurrence of antimicrobial resistances of some bacterial species from 'Kunun-Aya' drinks sold at University of Jos community Plateau State, Nigeria.

The prevalence of antimicrobial resistant bacteria obtained in this study could be due to the increased use/misuse of antibiotics in human medicine. However, the increased susceptibility of the isolates to the antibiotics tested perhaps can assist in the design of treatment regimen of infections due to these organisms. Therefore, consumption of this beverage has potential health hazard to the consumers.

The prevalence of antimicrobial consumers of this popular drink were therefore placed at health risk which may culminate into failures of commonly used clinical antibiotics for the treatment of infections.

Authors' declaration

We declared that this study is an original research by our research team and we agree to publish it in the journal.

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